

Welcome to the March newsletter, let's find out what your fellow LNLs have been getting up to and how you can sign up for future events.

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Joint LNL and IL meeting

Last week as part of the Community Project we held the first joint LNL and IL meeting in Glasgow. We're delighted to report that 16 IL and 20 LNL or their representatives attended, in some cases people represented both roles. Here's a photo taken the end of the day (several folk had left by then hence the reduced numbers). We started with brief presentations from Lisa De Bruine (former LNL now IL University of Glasgow), Joost Dessing, (LNL Queen's University Belfast), David Smailes (LNL ,Northumbria University) and Joe Corneli (ORCA looking to become LNL Oxford Brookes University) then Community Project Manager, Will Gawned, led a series of discussions around what you need to get the most out of your role? What can UKRN do to support career progression? And what are the priorities for UKRN? More on this in the next newsletter. In the meantime here are some photos of you lovely lot in conversation.

LNLs take part in institutional open research events

We invited several LNLs to take part in an event during the University of Liverpool [Open Research Week 2024](#). This included Michel Belyk (LNL Edgehill University), Krzysztof Cipora (LNL Loughborough University), Andrew Jones (LNL Liverpool John Moore's University), Osama Mahmoud (formerly LNL now IL University of Essex) and Alexis Makin (LNL University of Liverpool).

More LNLs will be speaking at the [Northumbria University Open Research Week 2024 on 21 March at 14:00](#)

Grant Abt (LNL University of Hull), Will Cawthorn (LNL University of Edinburgh) and David Smailes (LNL Northumbria University) will each be giving a short presentation and contributing to a Q&A session.

More details and registration [here](#)

Your LNL workshops

Workshop 1: Setting up a student consortium for undergraduate final year projects

A recording of the presentation by Kait Clark (LNL University of the West of England - UWE) is now [available](#). If anyone would like to be included in a future student consortium please contact Kait.

Workshop 2: Building the LNL – Open Research Enabler relationship

This workshop brought together LNLs and ORCAs (Open Research Coordinators & Administrators based at institutes involved in the UKRN Open Research Programme) to share their experiences and advice on how best to reach researchers in other disciplines and bring them into local network open research activities. It included presentations from Evangeline Gowie (ORCA University of Reading), Adam Patridge (previously an LNL now ORCA at University of Sheffield), Joe Corneli (ORCA now looking to become LNL at Oxford Brookes) and Steve Boneham (joint LNL & ORCA Newcastle University). A recording will be available shortly.

Next up is **workshop 3: Writing retreat – all day event**

This provides an opportunity for some light social activity, as well as carving out a solid block of time to dedicate to writing/coding/analysis. Set your out-of-office and devote maximum headspace to your task. The day will be led by Sarah Gunn, LNL University of Leicester.

4 April 9:30 – 16:00 (optional later finish at 17:30) Register [here](#)

Workshop 4: Understanding the workings of an institution

This will be presented by Etienne Roesch, former LNL now IL at University of Reading.

To deploy change at scale LNLs need institutional support. Etienne will share his experience of the practical steps needed to reach the right people in the right way, and how he used this understanding to develop policies within his institution.

2 May 13:00– 14:00 Register [here](#)

Workshop 5: Mindset awareness

This will be presented by Nikki Osborne, Director of [Responsible Research in Practice](#). An awareness of how mindset can impact research culture can help discussions on how to support change. The workshop will enable LNLs to work together on activities to understand more about fixed and growth mindsets, and to reflect on how these mindsets affect themselves and others

13 June 13:00pm – 14:00pm Register [here](#):

December workshop: Replication games – all day event

It's a long way off but we're so excited we wanted to share the details with you. This will be an all-day event run by Abel Brodeur from the [Institute for Replication](#). Consider it an early Christmas present from us to you. More details to follow

5 December 9:30 – 17:30 Register [here](#)

Would YOU like to run a workshop?

We still have a few slots left. Get in touch contact@ukrn.org

UKRN events

[Indicators for Open Research](#)

March 14 13:00 - 14:00

Very short notice on this one, but a recording will be made available in due course. Neil Jacobs will present work being coordinated via the UKRN Open Research Programme, to explore and develop indicators of open research. Register [here](#)

[UKRN Annual meeting](#)

March 22 10:00 - 16:00

Updates from across various UKRN activities, and announcing this year's winners of the Dorothy Bishop Prize. Register [here](#)

Update on Open Research Programme (ORP) Institutional Partners meeting

April 18 13:00 - 15:00

Neil Jacobs will provide an update on UKRN Open Research Programme activities. Register here

Other events

Software Sustainability Institute [Collaborations Workshop 2024 \(CW24\)](#)

University of Warwick, April 30 - May 2

The [Software Sustainability Institute](#) (SSI) works to support the UK's research software community across all domains and help improve practices, recognition, support and funding around open and reproducible computational research. The workshop consists of mini "show and tell" workshops and a number of discussion, collaborative ideas and hack sessions where members of different communities come together to explore important ideas in software and research and to plant the seeds of interdisciplinary collaborations. The themes of CW24 are Environmental Sustainability, AI/ML tools for science, and Citizen Science. [Registration](#) and [call for workshop/demo/lightning talk proposals](#) for CW24 are now open.

[The 3Hs Initiative: Housing, Handling and Habituation](#)

Improving the lives of laboratory rodents one lab at a time

March 27 14:00 - 15:00 UK time

A webinar to launch a website and training resource to promote best practice in animal research. The [3Hs initiative](#) focuses on housing, handling and habituation of laboratory rodents. The webinar will provide an introduction to the 3Hs concept and framework and demonstration of the new online resources. Register [here](#)

[Open Science Cluster Action for Research & Society \(OSCARS\)](#)

This four-year Horizon Europe project brings together world-class European research institutions with the goal of fostering the uptake of Open Science in Europe across scientific disciplines and communities. Please check their website [oscars-project.eu](#) for details about open calls. Registration for the 15th March launch call meeting has already closed, but Anca Hienola Anca.Hienola@fmi.fi from the Finnish Meteorological Institute Research Coordination group is happy to discuss any questions you may have. There will also be a second call in November 2024.

New UKRN Primers

[UKRN Primer on Community Engagement in Research](#)

Community engagement in research is a complex topic, with approaches varying between disciplines. This primer is aimed at researchers, particularly those who are new to community engagement. Full article [here](#)

[Open Research Champions Networks](#)

A primer to support institutions in setting up or running networks of Open Research Champions. UKRN would like to add to the supporting materials over the next year and so, if you can share documents related to your Champions network, please email neil.jacobs@bristol.ac.uk. Full article [here](#)

Image credit: Ag Ku - Pixabay

Other reading recommendations

A League of European Research Universities ([LERU](#)) publication - [Open Science and its role in universities: a roadmap for cultural change](#) More recent LERU publications can be found [here](#) (with thanks to Joost Dessing, LNL Queen's University, Belfast).

[Evading Open Science: The Black Box of Student Data Collection](#)

This paper explores student and supervisor perspectives, research practices and misconduct 'ranging from somewhat questionable to highly fraudulent' and the inclusion of student data in publications (with thanks to David Smailes, LNL Northumbria University).

[Is replication possible in qualitative research? A response to Makel et al. \(2022\)](#)

Article by Madeleine Pownall in which she encourages 'a more nuanced appraisal' of replication within qualitative research (with thanks to Mircea Zloteanu, LNL Kingston University, London).

Online resources

Research Culture Café graphics

Last year [GuildHE](#) Research ran a series of [Research Culture Cafés](#) to ask

what is research culture and how do you go about improving it? They encourage others to [download](#) the graphics to stimulate discussions about Research Culture. This work is part of the EU project Enhancing Trust, Integrity and Efficiency in Research through next-level Reproducibility ([TIER2](#))

All this could be yours

Become a guest editor! We hope you'll agree that this newsletter useful, a quick way of receiving updates on events or resources that you and your local network might be interested in. Would you like to contribute and article or become a guest editor? Just imagine, a whole issue dedicated to an area of open research close to your heart. Get in touch and we'll support you in making it a reality contact@ukrn.org

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